

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase

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Data principles and strategy for AgroEcoLLNet

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Deliverable Number	D6.5
Work Package	WP6
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Deliverable leader	LifeWatch ERIC
Due date	30 June 2023
Submission date	24 November 2023
Version	V1
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History of changes

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
V0.1	30/04/2021	Juan-Miguel González-Aranda, José-Manuel Avila-Castuera, Antonio-José Sáenz-Albanés	First draft
V0.2	30/04/2023	Daniel Caro Gómez, José-Manuel Avila-Castuera	Completed version including a preliminary definition of the principles and strategy
V0.3	30/07/2023	Daniel Caro Gómez	Inclusion of the questionnaire results and analysis
V0.4	31/10/2023	José Manuel Avila-Castuera	Consolidated version for review
V0.5	20/11/2023	Heather McKhann, Ophélie Bonnet	Revision
V1.0	20/11/2023	José Manuel Avila-Castuera	Final version

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Table of contents

1. INTRODUCTION	5
1.1 INNOVATION MANAGEMENT.....	6
1.2 OPEN SCIENCE, OPEN DATA AND FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES	7
1.3 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS	8
2. BARRIERS AND ENABLERS OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT, OPEN SCIENCE AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS IN AGROECOLOGY LIVING LABS AND RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES.....	10
2.1 METHODOLOGY: QUESTIONNAIRE STRUCTURE AND DESCRIPTION OF THE SAMPLE ...	11
2.2 ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRE	11
3. DATA PRINCIPLES AND STRATEGIES FOR THE EUROPEAN NETWORK OF AGROECOLOGY LIVING LABS AND RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES.....	16
3.1 DATA PRINCIPLES	16
3.2 DATA STRATEGY.....	18
3.3 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN.....	19
3.4 DATA GOVERNANCE MODELS.....	21
4. CONCLUSIONS	23
5. REFERENCES.....	25
6. ANNEX – QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS.....	30

List of abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable
H2020	Horizon 2020, EU's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LL	Living Lab
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
RI	Research Infrastructure
R&D	Research and Development
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

The landscape of modern agroecology is becoming increasingly complex in terms of the challenges it aims to address and the data-driven solutions it seeks to employ. In this context, the project ALL-Ready aims to stand as a model of integrated and multidisciplinary research. A central element of this effort is effective management and strategic use of data. Deliverable 6.5, "Principles and Data Strategy for AgroEcoLLNet," aims to outline the framework that will help members of the future EU Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs to properly manage data and intellectual property rights (IPR) under their innovation management strategy. This deliverable serves as the cornerstone for Task 6.4 *Innovation and IPR management*, which focuses on innovation and the management of IPR underpinning the entire data management ecosystem of the project.

The need for a coherent data strategy cannot be underestimated. As the world faces increasingly severe environmental crises, the ability to leverage data for informed decision-making becomes not just a scientific aspiration but a social imperative (Bellon-Maurel et al., 2022). Our approach to agroecological data management has far-reaching implications for sustainable agriculture, affecting farmers, policymakers, researchers, and ultimately consumers (Ali and Dahlhaus, 2022). Given the importance of data as a resource, its governance follows the same importance. Implementing rigorous data principles, such as those summarised in FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) guidelines (Wilkinson et al., 2016), is crucial to ensuring that data becomes a powerful tool rather than a bottleneck in the pursuit of sustainable agriculture (Ali and Dahlhaus, 2022).

Knowledge and Innovation management, access to LLs and RIs, and sharing of data are critical topics to face a real challenge for enhancing the innovation process and innovation management in agroecology. ALL-Ready is making an advance in the field of data sharing and innovation policies in order to foster agroecology transition based on innovation activities. This deliverable brings an analysis of how these fields apply to the Agroecology Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs). Starting from an analysis of how project partners identify data and IPR during the first stages of the project and continuing with an analysis of the practices from the members of the Pilot Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs, this deliverable provides a framework including data principles and strategy, including an implementation plan and data governance models that can be followed by the future EU Network of LLs and RIs.

This deliverable also underscores the notion that technology alone is insufficient to tackle these challenges. Human expertise remains a cornerstone for navigating the intricate landscape of agroecological data. From selecting datasets to ensuring ethical considerations in data collection and use, the role of human actors is invaluable.

This document addresses how we align the multiple, sometimes contrasting, facets of open science, open data and IPR into a unified data strategy. This strategy outlines data collection, storage, and sharing protocols driven by FAIR principles. It also identifies the importance of checkpoints to ensure data quality and integrity. The data strategy also considers the establishment of IPR principles and how compliance with the regulations should be monitored and enforced. Most importantly, it lays the groundwork for innovative approaches to managing and using agroecological data.

The ultimate goal is to make this strategy not just a guide but a living document that adapts to emerging needs and new insights, thereby acting as a catalyst for continuous improvement in agroecological data management. Therefore, it is designed flexibly, open to iterations and improvements as the future EU Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs progresses and new insights are gained. In this sense, it is not an end but a starting point in our ongoing journey towards a more sustainable and data-driven future for European agroecology.

1.1 Innovation management

Innovation is fundamentally about generating and applying new knowledge to improve and renew processes, products, and services (Baregheh et al., 2009). This principle holds importance across all fields, particularly agroecology, where the sustainability of the productive system is directly dependent on adaptability and evolution in the face of new challenges (López-Mosquera et al., 2014). As methodological and organisational tools, innovation management systems are essential instruments to promote and manage innovative ideas, aiming to systematise and optimise the innovation process (Adams et al., 2006; Francis et al., 2005). Globally, various regulations and standards guide the establishment and operation of these systems, with ISO 56002 being one of the most recognised (ISO 56002, 2019).

In the context of LLs and RIs, applying an innovation management system based on ISO or similar standards can be advantageous (Chesbrough, 2006). These organisations, characterised by their collaborative and experimentation-oriented approach (Greve et al., 2021; McPhee et al., 2021), can use innovation management systems to structure and formalise their innovation processes, ensuring all stages of the innovation cycle are considered, from idea generation to implementation and evaluation. These systems can help identify and manage innovation-associated risks and establish mechanisms to improve innovation activities continuously (Beaudoin et al., 2022; Lazzarotti et al., 2010). However, they also require significant human and financial resources and could necessitate considerable changes in the organisation and culture of the LLs or RIs (Lam, 2005).

In the sphere of agroecology, the implementation of an innovation management system in LLs and RIs can make a considerable difference. This system's collaborative approach is especially beneficial in addressing complex challenges associated with sustainable agricultural production (McPhee et al., 2021; Kamprath et al., 2013). Collaboration within this system can facilitate access to new ideas and knowledge, promoting the diffusion and adoption of innovations developed by the LLs or RIs. However, managing innovation in a multidisciplinary and rapidly evolving field like agroecology can be complex (Efrat, 2014). Therefore, LLs and RIs should strategically implement an innovation management system, considering their objectives, capabilities, and context (Zawislak et al., 2012). They should select a standard that

suits their needs, adapt it to their context, and establish mechanisms for continually assessing and improving their innovation management system to keep it relevant and effective (Meijer, 2015).

1.2 Open Science, Open Data and FAIR data principles

Open Science, which encompasses the concepts of Open Data, Data Access, and the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), are increasingly relevant concepts in Research and Development (R&D). Their goal is to promote transparency, collaboration, and efficiency in R&D, and they are becoming the norm in many disciplines and contexts (Hess et al., 2007). LLs and RIs engaged in the study of agroecology have much to gain from adopting these principles and practices, but they may also face specific challenges.

In particular, the European Union is promoting open access as part of an overarching Open Science strategy to enhance knowledge distribution and innovation. In line with this, the Commission has released the EC Recommendation C (2012) 4890 final on access to and preservation of scientific information. This document encourages every Member State to establish explicit policies to distribute and open access to scientific publications and data derived from publicly funded research. This initiative was set forth under the H2020 program and persists under the current Horizon Europe Framework Program.

Open Science is an R&D approach that promotes transparency and collaboration by sharing research results and the methods used to obtain them (Nielsen, 2011). Concurrently, Open Data and Data Access refer to making research data available in open repositories to a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, companies, and the general public (Borgman, 2012). By sharing this comprehensive set of information, the scientific community can validate results, replicate studies, conduct new analyses, and build upon existing work, thereby accelerating the progress of science and promoting transparency and trust (Woelfle et al., 2011; Tenopir et al., 2011).

The FAIR Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) are a set of guidelines designed to ensure that data is easily Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. These principles can be applied to research data and results and the methods used to obtain them.

In LLs and RIs engaged in the study of agroecology, adopting these principles and practices can have significant benefits. It can facilitate collaboration between different LLs and RIs and other actors, such as universities, companies, non-governmental organisations, and the general public (Ballon et al., 2018; Burgelman et al., 2019). This can be especially important in a multidisciplinary field like agroecology, where collaboration can allow for integrating different approaches and perspectives. In addition, Open Science, Open Data, Access to Data and the FAIR Principles can facilitate the replication and validation of research results, increasing confidence in them and in science in general (McKiernan et al., 2016). This may be especially relevant in agroecology, where research results directly affect agricultural practice and policy. Ultimately, these principles and practices can facilitate using data and research results to develop new solutions, products, and services that can accelerate innovation, especially in LLs (West et al., 2014).

However, adopting these principles and practices can also present challenges for LLs and RIs (McPhee et al., 2021). On the one hand, they may require significant changes in how R&D is performed and managed, including changes in the organisation's culture, work practices, and information and data management systems (Leonelli, 2016). On the other hand, privacy and data security concerns may arise, especially in the case of sensitive data (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014). Additionally, technical and logistical challenges may be associated with managing and storing the data, and preparing it for publication in the open format (Wallis et al., 2013).

Therefore, LLs and RIs who adopt these principles and practices must do so strategically, considering their objectives, capabilities, and context. They should establish clear policies and practices for data and information management, including data privacy and security, and provide training and support for their staff to adopt these new practices (Kratz et al., 2015).

1.3 Intellectual Property Rights

Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) are crucial to the contemporary research and innovation landscape. These rights, including patents, copyrights, or trade secrets, provide legal protections for creators and innovators, potentially fostering innovation by protecting and rewarding creativity and investment (Hall et al., 2014). However, when applied to the context of LLs and RIs focused on agroecology, the intersection of IPRs with Open Science, Open Data, Data Access, and FAIR principles poses unique considerations and challenges.

Conventionally, IPRs protect R&D investments, offering an exclusive right to exploit an invention for a specified period. This exclusivity helps ensure a return on investment, incentivising further innovation (Hall et al., 2014). Yet, this traditional view of IPRs may seem at odds with the principles of Open Science and Open Data, which advocate for free and open access to research findings and data to foster scientific progress (Murray et al., 2007).

Managing IPRs in such a context needs a delicate balance. Several emerging models blend IPR protections with open access principles, often called "managed openness" (Garcia Llorente et al., 2019). Under such a framework, some aspects of the research might be patented or otherwise protected, while others are shared openly. This approach can safeguard core innovations while facilitating scientific collaboration and learning (Chesbrough, 2014).

For example, organisations might choose to protect certain "core" innovations that offer a competitive advantage, while "peripheral" findings and data might be shared openly. This selective approach to IPR can foster both innovation and openness. However, implementing such a strategy requires careful consideration and management of what constitutes "core" and "peripheral" knowledge (Chesbrough, 2006).

Additionally, alternative forms of IPRs such as "open patents" and "creative commons" licenses, may provide some resolution (Contreras, 2011). Open patents, for instance, involve patent holders agreeing not to enforce their patents against parties who use their technology for certain purposes, often for research or for non-profit purposes. Similarly, Creative Commons licenses provide a way to offer certain rights to the public while reserving others (Sridhar, 2019).

LLs and RIs in the field of agroecology are uniquely positioned in this scenario. On the one hand, they strive for innovation in a discipline with profound societal implications, improving sustainability and resilience in our food systems (Dedeurwaerdere, 2014). On the other hand, they grapple with the requirement for open and shared knowledge to foster collaboration and accelerate scientific progress.

It's crucial to note that managing IPRs in the context of Open Science and Open Data requires a clear understanding of IPR laws and policies and an organisational culture that values both protection and openness (Del Giudice et al., 2018). Furthermore, the benefits of openness should not be underestimated: open access to research findings and data can lead to higher citation rates, increased collaboration, and accelerated scientific progress (Piwowar et al., 2018).

1.3.1 Analysis of Intellectual Property Rights in the Consortium Agreement of ALL-Ready

IPR are a cornerstone in modern research and development architecture, governing how we share, protect, and build upon innovative ideas and technologies. Within the ALL-Ready project, understanding the IPR landscape is a formality and a necessity for creating a cooperative and progressive research environment. To guide our strategies for joint IPR handling and establish a strong foundation for enduring collaboration, we have relied on the project Consortium Agreement (CA). The CA serves as our reference guide for navigating the complex interplay of protecting intellectual property while promoting open access and transparency. An analysis of the IPR provisions within this agreement provides invaluable insights into the consortium's collective stance on innovation management, data sharing, and IPR protections, among other aspects.

This deliverable aims to analyse the IPR terms outlined in the CA, examining their implications across various facets of the project, i.e., innovation management, open data practices, and comprehensive IPR management. The outcomes of this analysis are instrumental in shaping our strategies and policies going forward. Through this lens, we scrutinise the conditions set by consortium partners, elucidate limitations, and propose standardised approaches for effectively balancing the imperatives of IPR protection and open science.

The findings from this rigorous analysis will serve as the foundation for future recommendations, thereby aiding the consortium in navigating the nuanced landscape of IPR in the context of agroecological research and innovation. This will ensure that ALL-Ready not only adheres to legal and ethical norms but also maximises its work's shared value and impact, ultimately contributing to the sustainable development of the agroecology sector.

The limitations and conditions set by the ALL-READY consortium partners have implications for each of the areas highlighted in this document: innovation management, open data practices, and comprehensive IPR management. Implementing standard approaches in these areas could help the consortium navigate the conditions set by its partners and promote a model of managed openness that upholds both IPR and open science principles, thereby contributing to the sustainable development of the agroecology innovation sector.

The main lessons learnt from the CA analysis are:

- When we consider innovation management, the stipulated conditions underscore the importance of recognising and respecting the intellectual contributions of each partner. Citations, for instance, are a vital aspect of this recognition. Additionally, the diverse set of conditions and exclusions, especially those that limit the sharing of certain background information or software, points to the need for more formalised and standard approaches to managing innovation within the consortium. This could help provide predictability and consistency and address some of the limitations set by individual partners.
- Concerning open data use, the limitations specified by the partners highlight the need for formalised open data practices. Specifically, respecting the data exclusions set by the partners necessitates a formalised approach to data management, ensuring that data use within the consortium aligns with individual partners' requirements. Additionally, the limitations set forth by partners on their data's use underscore the need for enhanced training and awareness of open science principles to ensure that data is shared and utilised ethically and responsibly.
- Regarding comprehensive IPR management, the various conditions and exclusions set by partners underscore the importance of protecting IPR within the consortium. For example, citing sources and excluding certain background information underlines the necessity for robust IPR practices. A lack of clear information about explicit exclusion for some resources evidenced the need for clear IPR strategies within the consortium, including protecting innovative ideas and procedures for addressing IPR infringements.

In general, this analysis provides evidence for the need for more information, clear data, and knowledge-sharing strategies for partners working on agroecology in a collaborative R&D project. ALL-Ready has developed different deliverables in WP6 Data and Knowledge Management to improve this scenario to help project partners enhance data management to foster collaboration and create new knowledge. Moreover, these lessons have also inspired the data principles and strategies provided in this document.

2. Barriers and Enablers of innovation management, open science and Intellectual Property Rights in Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures

The ALL-Ready project aims to help the future network of Agroecology LLs and RIs in the management of data and knowledge. To achieve this objective, we have first identified potential drivers and barriers to adopting innovation management, open science, and IPR among the members of the Pilot Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs (Varga, et al. 2023). The ALL-Ready Pilot Network is made up of RIs as well as LLs working in the field of agroecology, so the way they manage innovation, use open data and ultimately take advantage of the results obtained provides essential

information that can help to design the data principles and strategies for the future EU Network.

One of the main challenges identified in the previous phases of the project implementation is that the innovations and developments require an end-to-end data management approach to ensure quality while adopting FAIR principles along the data path (Ávila et al., 2021). While the project aims at collecting extensive, multidisciplinary data in a standardised manner by using open specifications for existing agroecology data infrastructures, task 6.4 provides new opportunities for enhancing innovation processes and paving the way for releasing an efficient IPR management mechanism.

We, therefore, designed an online survey addressed to all members included in the ALL-Ready Pilot Network, which included RIs and LLs in order to gather information on what helps and what hinders these network members from adopting innovation management, open science, and IPR practices that are seen as vital for agroecology transition.

This report will allow an understanding of the current practices and potential drivers and barriers to adopting innovation management, open science and IPR among the members of the Pilot Network.

2.1 Methodology: questionnaire structure and description of the sample

The questionnaire was designed by LifeWatch ERIC and implemented through an online survey. LifeWatch ERIC analysed results. The questionnaire (Annex 1) consisted of 26 questions divided into four different sections: the first section set out the main information concerning LLs and RIs. The second, third and fourth sections focus on understanding existing practices, potential drivers (factors encouraging the change), and barriers (factors impeding the change) related to adopting innovation management, open science, and IPR for each member. Each section has been subdivided into subsections in the analysis process to get the best understanding of each topic.

The survey was addressed to all members included in the ALL-Ready Pilot Network, taking one contact person per member. The total number of contacts that received the invitation was 15. There were no bounce-backs due to incorrect or outdated contact information; therefore, the total number of recipients was 15. There were 10 valid responses to the survey by the deadline of 20 June 2023. This represents a response rate of about 67%.

2.2 Analysis of questionnaire

2.2.1 Block 1: General data

The typology of an entity that accounted for the highest number of survey responses was LL (70%), and the rest was Research Infrastructure (30%). These results are in line with the percentage distribution of the entities participating in the Pilot Network. Here are some additional thoughts on the text:

2.2.2 Block 2: Innovation Management, potential drivers and barriers

"Most respondents state that the Lack of resources, both in terms of time and funding, and Resistance to change stand as the most prominent barriers to effective innovation management"

This block aims to evaluate the current state of innovation management in LLs and RIs dedicated to agroecology. The questions in this block focus on the processes, methodologies and tools used to manage innovation in these environments. Innovation management is the process of devising, developing and commercialising new ideas. It is a complex process that requires the participation of a variety of actors, including researchers, entrepreneurs, users and others. LLs and RIs dedicated to agroecology play an important role in innovation management. These environments provide a space for researchers and users to collaborate in developing new solutions to agroecology problems.

The questions in this block have been subdivided into four sub-blocks of interest.

- *Sub-Block 2.1: Innovation Process and Management (Questions 2.1 -2.4)*
This Sub-Block focuses on understanding how the innovation process is structured and managed. Half of the organisations have a formalised and documented process, while the other half operate more informally. The most widely used methodologies to facilitate innovation management include Agile and Design Thinking, emphasising adaptability, iteration, and user-centred problem-solving. However, some organisations do not apply a specific methodology, indicating a possible area for improvement.
- *Sub-Block 2.2: Evaluation of Innovations (Question 2.5)*
This section revolves around how the outcomes or success of these innovations are evaluated. Organisations reported a variety of good practices in innovation management, including bottom-up approaches, formal expression of needs, automation of prototyping and data processing, and cooperation with users and external stakeholders. However, there appears to be a lack of consistency in how the success of innovations is measured and evaluated, with some organisations not undertaking systematic evaluation.
- *Sub-Block 2.3: Collaboration in Innovation (Question 2.6)*
Most of the institutions surveyed believe in the value of collaborating with external stakeholders as part of their innovation process, although the frequency of this collaboration varies.
- *Sub-Block 2.4: Challenges and Benefits in Innovation Management (Questions 2.7 - 2.8)*
The most common barriers to innovation appear to be lack of resources, followed by resistance to change and the lack of a clear innovation strategy. However, key drivers for effective innovation management include improved efficiency and productivity, more successful project outcomes, and increased customer satisfaction.

The findings from the four sub-blocks of this section present a comprehensive overview of innovation processes within the sampled organisations. The results indicate a split between formal and informal approaches to innovation process management (Sub-Block 2.1). While half of the organisations have a formalised structure, including the application of Agile and Design Thinking methodologies, the remaining half are more informal, suggesting a potential area for development. Utilising well-defined methodologies can improve the predictability and repeatability of the innovation process, increasing the potential for successful outcomes (Hidalgo et al., 2008). The evaluation of innovations (Sub-Block 2.2) presents an inconsistency across organisations, with some lacking a systematic approach. Regular and structured evaluations are critical in innovation management, allowing for iterative improvements and ensuring alignment with organisational goals (Adams et al., 2006). The perceived value of external collaboration in innovation (Sub-Block 2.3) is high, reflecting the increasing shift towards open innovation models which leverage external knowledge to augment internal capacities (Greve et al., 2021; Chesbrough, 2006). Lastly, organisations identified a lack of resources, resistance to change, and the absence of clear innovation strategies as barriers to innovation (Sub-Block 2.4). Conversely, key drivers include improved efficiency, successful project outcomes, and customer satisfaction. Addressing these barriers and focusing on the drivers could enhance the effectiveness of innovation management (Adams et al., 2006).

These results highlight the need for a more consistent, formalised approach to innovation management and evaluation, as well as the recognition of the benefits of external collaboration and strategic planning in overcoming challenges and enhancing innovation effectiveness.

2.2.3 Block 3: Open Data Usage, potential drivers and barriers

"Data privacy and security concerns, reluctance to share data, and lack of technical skills or understanding are significant hurdles"

This block aims to evaluate the current state of open science and open data practices in Agroecology LLs and RIs. The questions in this block focus on awareness, training, and the use of open science and open data principles and practices in these settings. Open science is a movement that seeks to make scientific research more accessible, transparent and collaborative. Meanwhile, open data refers to those available for anyone to use, with no restrictions on access or use. LLs and RIs dedicated to agroecology play an important role in open science and open data, as these environments provide a space for researchers to share their data and results with other researchers, users and the general public.

The questions in this block have been subdivided into four sub-blocks of interest.

- *Sub-Block 3.1: Open Science and Data Policies (questions 3.1-3.3)*
This Sub-Block focuses on the institutions' policies and initiatives related to open science and data. Looking at the responses regarding open science and data policies, the practices varied among the surveyed organisations. Six organisations had formal, documented policies or practices to facilitate open

science and the use of open data, two had informal, undocumented practices, and three reported having no specific policies or practices. Regarding specific initiatives to promote and foster the use of open science and open data, five organisations reported having such initiatives, while six did not. Some examples were provided, such as implementing a Data Management Plan (DMP) and publishing open science metadata.

- *Sub-Block 3.2: Data Availability and Quality (questions 3.4-3.5)*

This Sub-Block 3.2 included questions about the availability and quality assurance of the open data. In terms of the availability and quality of open data, a variety of data types were made available by the organisations, including raw data from experiments or observations, processed or analysed data, metadata, data from literature reviews or bibliographic data, social or economic data, geographic or spatial data, environmental data, genetic or biological data, digital technology data, and data from digital sensors in agricultural lands. Some organisations reported not currently providing any open data. Quality assurance methods also varied, with some organisations using regular audits/reviews, data standards, and training for data creators/providers, while others reported not using any specific methods.

- *Sub-Block 3.3: Training in Open Science and Data (questions 3.6)*

None of the organisations reported conducting regular training sessions in open science and open data. Two organisations used online courses or resources, three used one-to-one mentoring, and six reported no specific training methods. One respondent mentioned that farmers were not interested in this kind of training and that researchers were responsible for and trained in open access.

- *Sub-Block 3.4: Challenges and Benefits in Open Science/Data (questions 3.7-3.9)*

The main challenges or barriers faced by the organisations in terms of open science and open data were the reluctance of users to share their data, a lack of awareness or understanding of open science principles, insufficient technical skills or knowledge, data privacy and security concerns, lack of resources or funding, and lack of time. Some methods to overcome these barriers included collaborating with other institutions, additional training, increased funding or resources, and updating incentives within the scientific system. Key advantages or drivers of promoting open science and open data were enhanced research transparency, more significant collaboration opportunities, wider dissemination of research findings, accelerated innovation, and increased public trust in research. The survey results paint a varied picture of open science and data practices across the participating organisations. The responses present a diverse spectrum of policies and practices concerning open science and data. While some organisations have formal policies or initiatives, such as DMPs and open science metadata publishing, others lack specific practices, pointing towards a potential gap in the uniform adoption of open science principles (Roche et al., 2020). The questionnaire reveals that a range of data types is made available, reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of agroecological research. However, quality assurance methods diverge, with some organisations not employing specific strategies, highlighting the need for standardised data quality and integrity measures (Borgman, 2012). Training in open science and data, as observed in Sub-Block 3.3, is another area for improvement. The absence of regular training sessions and lack of interest from some stakeholders indicate the need for proactive efforts to increase

awareness and enhance skills related to open science and data (Tenopir et al., 2017). Finally, results showed several challenges, including reluctance to share data, lack of awareness, technical skills, resources, and privacy concerns. These can be addressed through collaboration, additional training, increased funding, and updated incentives. Benefits of open science and data practices underline its importance for research transparency, collaboration, dissemination, innovation, and public trust (Woelfle et al., 2011). Overall, the results highlight opportunities for improving open science practices, such as instituting formal policies, ensuring data quality, and promoting training and awareness, enhancing potential benefits and overcoming associated challenges.

2.2.4 Block 4: Intellectual Property Rights, potential drivers and barriers

"Understanding complex IPR regulations, and the time and cost associated with IPR, stand as significant challenges"

The objective of this block is to assess the current state of intellectual property (IP) practices in Agroecology LLs and RIs. The questions in this block focus on awareness, training, and use of IP principles and practices in these settings.

The questions in this block have been subdivided into four sub-blocks of interest.

- *Sub-Block 4.1: IPR Management and Protection Practices (Questions 4.1- 4.5)*
These questions address how organisations handle and protect their IPRs. Respondents indicated that most of the surveyed entities lack specific practices or strategies for managing IPR, which might hint towards insufficient awareness or training in this area. It also revealed varied strategies employed for intellectual property protection, with trademarks and trade secrets somewhat more commonly mentioned.
- *Sub-Block 4.2: Handling of IPR Infringements (Question 4.6)*
This question focuses on the procedures in place to deal with violations of IPRs. Most respondents stated that they do not possess a specific process for handling IPR infringements, suggesting a potential obstacle to the adequate protection of intellectual property.
- *Sub-Block 4.3: Challenges and Benefits of IPR Management (Questions 4.7 and 4.8)*
These questions explore the main obstacles and motivations related to IPRs management. According to responses, the complexity of IPR regulations and the associated time and cost were identified as significant challenges. The benefits or drivers for robust IPR management, as indicated by responses to 4.8, primarily included protection of innovative ideas, prevention of misuse of proprietary information, and enhancement of the organisation's reputation.

The survey responses highlighted significant opportunities for improvement in the domain of IPR management and protection among the surveyed organisations. The answers provided evidence that many of these organisations lack specific practices

or strategies for managing IPR, suggesting a possible deficiency in awareness or training about IPR, as stated by Pila (2017). The methods employed for protecting intellectual property, such as trademarks and trade secrets, seem to vary widely, hinting at a lack of standardisation. The absence of specific procedures to handle IPR infringements among most respondents signalled a potential gap in the effective protection of intellectual property. This lack of preparedness could be detrimental in scenarios where swift and decisive action is needed to address such violations (Torremans, 2016). In addition, the responses underlined the complexities of IPR regulations, time, and cost as significant hurdles, a sentiment referenced in the literature (Long, 2010). However, respondents also identify valuable drivers for efficient IPR management, including protecting innovative ideas, preventing proprietary information misuse, and enhancing the organisation's reputation. Overall, these findings highlight the need for systematic IPR management practices, awareness, and training. By tackling these issues, organisations can more effectively protect their intellectual property and leverage it for innovation and reputation enhancement.

3. Data principles and strategies for the European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures

In the evolving field of agroecology, precision is key. Proper data principles ensure consistent and accurate data collection, a cornerstone for robust research. A strategic framework is critical as diverse stakeholders, from farmers to policymakers, rely on this research. It ensures data is managed systematically, fostering trust and facilitating collaborative efforts. Without such guidelines, data can become fragmented, leading to potential inaccuracies. Moreover, a solid strategy ensures data is used purposefully, maximising its impact by directing research towards meaningful, actionable insights that can drive sustainable agricultural practices forward.

Based on the previous work from ALL-Ready WP6 Knowledge and Data Management (Ávila et al., 2021a,b), the specific literature review and the questionnaire results, a conceptual framework has been consolidated. This conceptual framework aims to serve as a basis for understanding how establishing data principles and a strategy for agroecology LLs and RIs is essential to ensure that data is collected, managed, and used responsibly, effectively, and purposefully.

3.1 Data principles

1. **Openness and Transparency:** It's vital to adopt open science principles, making research data, methodologies, and findings publicly accessible. This includes publishing research outputs in open-access journals when possible. It is also important to promote open science practices, such as sharing research protocols, code, and data openly, to encourage collaboration, verification, and reuse by the scientific community.

2. **FAIR Data Principles:** These principles advocate for data to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. In essence:

- Findable: Data and metadata should be easily located by both humans and computers.
- Accessible: Once found, the data and metadata should be accessible, where possible, through open interfaces.
- Interoperable: Data must be usable in diverse applications or workflows for analysis, storage, etc.
- Reusable: Data must be maintained and validated in a way that they can be reused with confidence.

Following the FAIR data principles involves providing metadata, persistent identifiers, and clear licensing to facilitate data discovery and reuse.

3. **Ethical Data Collection and Use:** It's essential to acquire informed consent from participants and pay special attention to privacy and confidentiality concerns in order to ensure that data collection and use are conducted ethically.

4. **Interoperability and Standardisation:** Interoperability refers to computer systems' ability to exchange and use information. It's critical for sharing and merging data from different projects and institutions. On the other hand, standardisation helps maintain consistency in data collection, interpretation, and usage. Promoting data standardisation and interoperability is key to enabling seamless data sharing and integration across different projects and institutions.

5. **Data Quality and Integrity:** Data quality involves precision, accuracy, and reliability in data collection, ensuring trustworthy research conclusions. Data integrity, meanwhile, safeguards against unintentional modifications, providing consistency from data collection to analysis and fostering trust in the research process. Maintaining high data quality, accuracy, and integrity is advisable to ensure the credibility and reliability of research outcomes.

6. **Inclusivity and Diversity:** It is recommendable to address biases and promote inclusivity in data collection and representation to include diverse perspectives and knowledge systems.

7. **Sustainability:** Practices and infrastructures must be sustainable in the long run, guaranteeing the availability and accessibility of data for future research. Thus, it is key to implement practices that ensure that data remains available and accessible for future research.

3.2 Data strategy

Elaborating a Data Strategy is foundational for structuring the myriad data elements that arise from research efforts, especially in domains as dynamic and intricate as agroecology. The ALL-Ready project, as emphasised in previous deliverables D6.1 *Standards & protocols for FAIR data management identification* and D6.2 *Data Management Plan for ALL-Ready* (Ávila et al., 2021 a,b), provides pivotal pointers for structuring this strategy.

1. Data Collection and Management:

As stated in previous deliverables such as D6.1 *Standards & protocols for FAIR data management identification*, emphasising the importance of robust methodologies and technological backing, it is evident that utilising the latest and most effective techniques and tools for data collection, management, and analysis is crucial. Given that each data point is collected with a future analytical intent, it's vital to establish structured protocols and embrace data collection methods aligned with open science and FAIR principles, thereby promoting data sharing and reuse.

2. Data Sharing and Access:

Establishing data repositories or platforms that adhere to a well-structured data-sharing paradigm rooted in the FAIR principles accelerates collective problem-solving and innovation, enabling easy data discovery and access by stakeholders and the wider research community. Additionally, the use of open licenses and clear terms of use promote data sharing while respecting intellectual property and privacy rights.

3. Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Agroecology encompasses a spectrum of data, ranging from intricate soil analyses to overarching climate trends. Drawing from insights in D6.1 *Standards & protocols for FAIR data management identification*, the adoption of advanced analytical tools becomes pivotal for a comprehensive understanding. Advocating for the use of open-source data analysis tools and software is not just about ensuring transparency and reproducibility in research outcomes. It's also about fostering a collaborative milieu where scholars and data experts come together, culminating in shared learning and an expanded collective knowledge base.

4. Data Visualisation and Communication:

The efficacy of research lies in its ability to be communicated effectively. To that end, the power of intuitive visualisation tools becomes evident. They serve as a conduit, transforming complex research results into comprehensible insights for a varied audience, from policymakers to farmers. It's essential to craft user-friendly data visualisation tools and resources that seamlessly convey findings to diverse groups, ensuring that farmers, policymakers, and the general public alike can grasp the implications.

5. Capacity Building and Training:

Given the dynamic nature of agroecological research, continuous skill enhancement becomes indispensable. Customised training programs, sensitive to regional and cultural variations, play a crucial role in this progression. It's vital to provide training on open science and data management principles, ensuring that researchers, stakeholders, and data managers immersed in agroecology LLs and RIs are well-equipped and updated.

6. Data Governance and Ethics:

Embedded in the foundational values of the ALL-Ready project, there's a profound emphasis on the ethical management of data. Drawing inspiration from the guidelines of Deliverable D6.2 *Data Management Plan for ALL-Ready*, we can establish a data governance structure that not only aligns with open science principles but also safeguards the integrity and trustworthiness of data and ensures ethical data practices throughout the research process (See Section 3.4).

7. Long-term Data Preservation:

Securing the longevity of research data is a cornerstone of sustainable scientific endeavours. By implementing data archiving and preservation strategies that adhere to open science and FAIR data principles, we not only uphold the integrity of the data but also guarantee its accessibility for future researchers and stakeholders (See D6.1 *Data Management Plan for ALL-Ready*). This proactive approach ensures that valuable insights aren't lost over time and can continue to inform and impact the field of study for generations to come.

8. Monitoring and Evaluation:

LLs and RIs should monitor the adherence to open science and FAIR data principles and evaluate the impact of these practices on research outcomes and collaboration to ensure the proper adoption of the proposed strategy. Moreover, feedback loops ensure the strategy remains agile, adjusting to the ever-evolving agroecological research landscape.

3.3 Implementation Plan

A roadmap including timelines, responsibilities, and resource allocation will ensure the successful adoption of the proposed data principles and strategy. In the development of this roadmap it is recommended to collaborate with relevant stakeholders to ensure buy-in and support for the strategy's successful execution. Below, we suggest an implementation plan that agroecology LLs and RIs can follow. The timeline is indicative and should be adapted to the institution's context.

1. Phase 1: Pre-Implementation (0-3 months)

- Establish a dedicated data management team or committee responsible for overseeing the implementation of the data strategy.
- Conduct an assessment of existing data practices, infrastructure, and resources to identify gaps and areas for improvement.

- Define the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders involved in data collection, management, analysis, and sharing.

2. Phase 2: Data Collection and Management (3-6 months)

- Develop data collection protocols, dictionaries, and standardised formats to ensure consistent and high-quality data.
- Identify suitable data management tools and systems, considering scalability, security, and interoperability factors.
- Train researchers, field technicians, and farmers on data collection methods and data entry procedures.

3. Phase 3: Data Governance, Sharing and Access (6-9 months)

- Develop and implement a data governance framework that addresses data ownership, access rights, and ethical considerations.
- Establish a data-sharing policy that outlines the conditions and procedures for data sharing among researchers and stakeholders.
- Set up a secure and accessible data repository or platform for sharing and archiving data.
- Obtain necessary permissions and consent from participants for data sharing, especially when dealing with sensitive or private information.
- Establish protocols for data handling and protection to ensure compliance with relevant data protection regulations.

4. Phase 4: Data Analysis and Interpretation (9-12 months)

- Train researchers and data analysts on data analysis techniques relevant to agroecology and sustainability.
- Implement data analysis workflows and best practices, emphasising transparency and reproducibility.
- Encourage collaboration among researchers to leverage expertise and knowledge from different disciplines.

5. Phase 5: Data Visualisation and Communication (12-15 months)

- Develop data visualisation templates and guidelines to present research findings in a visually engaging and accessible manner.
- Organise workshops or webinars to communicate research outcomes to diverse stakeholders, including farmers and policymakers.
- Consider translating data visualisations and summaries into local languages for wider reach and understanding.

6. Phase 6: Long-term Data Preservation (15-18 months, but depend on the characteristics of data)

- Develop a plan for long-term data preservation and archiving to ensure data availability for future research and reference.

- Explore opportunities for collaboration with data repositories or data preservation networks.
- Long-term data protocols require the design of long-term data preservation and archiving at the beginning of the process.

7. Phase 7: Capacity Building and Training (ongoing)

- Organise capacity-building workshops and training sessions for farmers and local communities on data literacy and data-driven decision-making.
- Empower stakeholders to participate in data collection and interpretation processes actively.

8. Phase 8: Monitoring and Evaluation (Ongoing)

- Implement a monitoring and evaluation system to assess the effectiveness of the data strategy in achieving its objectives.
- Regularly review and update the data strategy based on feedback and emerging needs.

9. Phase 9: Continuous Improvement (Ongoing)

- Foster a culture of continuous improvement by encouraging feedback, learning from successes and challenges, and adapting the strategy accordingly.
- Celebrate achievements and milestones to motivate stakeholders and maintain their engagement.

3.4 Data Governance Models

Addressing the question of data governance is of utmost importance, as data grants significant power to those with access and processing capabilities (Bellon-Maurel, et al. 2022). Data governance schemes are crucial to ensure proper handling, security and interoperability of data (Micheli et al., 2020; Ladley, 2019; Carolan, 2017; Bronson and Knezevic, 2016). Below is a description of some data governance models that can be applied in LLs or RIs.

1. Centralised Governance Model

In a centralised model, a central data governance team is responsible for all decisions related to data management. This approach is especially useful for smaller LLs or RIs, where consistency and uniformity in data management are crucial. A central team sets policies, ensures compliance, and maintains data quality. This model is efficient but may be less flexible when adapting to the specific needs of different projects or departments.

Advantages:

- Greater consistency in data management.
- Facilitates compliance with regulations and standards.

- Lower risk of duplication of efforts.

Disadvantages:

- Less flexibility to adapt to specific needs.
- May create bottlenecks if the centralised team is overloaded.

2. Decentralised Governance Model

In contrast to the centralised model, the decentralised model allows each project or research unit to have its own data governance team. This approach is especially useful for large RIs with multiple ongoing projects, where each project may have unique data requirements. However, this model may lead to inconsistency in data management and require additional effort to ensure interoperability between different units.

Advantages:

- Greater flexibility to adapt to different project needs.
- Facilitates innovation and adaptability.

Disadvantages:

- Risk of inconsistency in data management.
- Greater complexity to ensure compliance with regulations.

3. Hybrid Governance Model

The hybrid model combines elements of centralised and decentralised models to create a more balanced approach. In this model, a central team sets general policies and guidelines, while decentralised teams adapt these guidelines to the specific needs of their projects. This approach offers a balance between the efficiency of the centralised model and the flexibility of the decentralised model.

Advantages:

- Balance between consistency and flexibility.
- Facilitates both compliance with regulations and adaptability to specific needs.

Disadvantages:

- Requires effective communication between centralised and decentralised teams.
- May be more complex to implement and manage.

4. Federated Governance Model

The federated model is especially useful for RIs that involve collaboration between multiple institutions or countries. In this model, each collaborating entity maintains a degree of autonomy in managing its data but also adheres to a set of common policies and guidelines. This ensures both consistency and flexibility in data management.

Advantages:

- Facilitates collaboration between multiple entities.
- Allows a degree of autonomy for each collaborating entity.

Disadvantages:

- Requires a common governance framework that all entities must accept.
- May be complex to implement at a logistical and legal level.

5. Project-Oriented Model

In the project-oriented model, data governance is organised around specific research projects. This approach is useful for LLs that operate based on external funding and may have different needs and requirements for data governance. Each project has its own data governance team, which dissolves once the project is completed.

Advantages:

- Allows highly specific and adapted data management for each project.
- Facilitates resource allocation based on project needs.

Disadvantages:

- May lead to fragmentation of data management.
- Requires effective transition of data governance once the project is completed.

4. Conclusions

This work reflects on how innovation management, open science and open data are essential in the context of agroecology LLs and RIs. The content of this text aims to contribute to the paradigm shift promoted by the European Union under the Open Science context. This paradigm shift, applied to agroecology, can be a cohesive force capable of driving systemic change in the field of sustainable agriculture. Being rooted in rigorous principles and guided by a well-structured strategy, it paves the way for a scientific, ethical, and equitable agroecological transformation.

The imperative of sustainable agriculture is no longer a point of academic debate, but a global imperative, especially in the face of climate change and resource

depletion. With its intrinsically interdisciplinary nature, agroecology offers a comprehensive perspective to address these challenges. However, the strength of this scientific field lies not only in its theoretical foundations but in its practical application, driven by solid guidelines and data methodologies. As detailed in this document, among its various objectives, the European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs is committed to establishing a comprehensive framework aimed at catalysing the transition towards the implementation of agroecological principles. This framework places significant emphasis on optimal data and knowledge management and underlines the importance of fostering improved interactions between RIs and LLs to accelerate these transitions.

The survey conducted with the Pilot Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs highlighted diverse approaches to innovation, open science and data practices, and IPR management within organisations. While some employ structured innovation methodologies, others lack systematic evaluation methods. Open science adoption varies, indicating a potential gap in uniform practices. Quality assurance methods for available data types differ, emphasising the need for standardisation. Training in open science is lacking, and challenges include data sharing reluctance and privacy concerns. Regarding IPR management, there is a lack of awareness and standardisation, with varying methods for protecting intellectual property.

The importance of a common approach that brings data principles and strategies together with an implementation plan can help future members of the network to target these areas following a systematic approach. Among the principles, the emphasis on openness and transparency, FAIR data principles, and ethical data collection and use cannot be understated. These principles facilitate scientific rigour, but also they ensure that science serves the public good. The data generated becomes an enabler for collaborative and transdisciplinary problem solving, involving stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, from farmers to policymakers. These lofty ideals are supported by meticulous data strategies to foster quality, integrity, standardisation and interoperability.

Additionally, data strategies focused on collection, sharing, analysis, interpretation, visualisation, and communication are essential for translating research into actionable insights. The power of this knowledge is multiplied when it is enhanced through training and education, particularly when adapted to local cultural and environmental contexts. Data governance and ethics principles serve as an ethical backbone, ensuring that the human element—privacy, consent, and equal participation—remains inviolable in the race for data-driven decisions.

In addition to the critical aspects discussed, it is necessary to highlight the role of Data Governance Models in the context of agroecology research. Effective data governance is foundational for ensuring data quality, security, and lifecycle management. It serves as a linchpin for the responsible management of data assets, thereby complementing IPR strategies.

Sustainability is the cornerstone, not only in the context of agroecological practices, but also in data management and preservation. The longevity of this data is not an afterthought but rather a prerequisite, as it ensures that future researchers and stakeholders continue to benefit from past knowledge. All of these pillars are subject to rigorous monitoring and evaluation mechanisms that not only measure effectiveness but also infuse the system with agility. This will be crucial, especially in

the rapidly evolving landscape of agroecological research and global sustainability challenges.

5. References

The ALL-Ready deliverables with a public dissemination level will all be available on Zenodo once approved by the EC.

Adams, R., Bessant, J., & Phelps, R. (2006). Innovation management measurement: A review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 8(1), 21-47.

Ali, B. & Dahlhaus, P. (2022). The Role of FAIR Data towards Sustainable Agricultural Performance: A Systematic Literature Review. *Agriculture* 12(2), 309.

Avila, J. M., Loppin, C., Sáenz-Albanés, A.-J., McKann, H., & González-Aranda, J. M. (2021). ALL-Ready - Standards & protocols for FAIR data management identification. ALL-Ready H2020 Project. <https://zenodo.org/records/8154622>

Avila, J.M., Sáenz-Albanés, A.J., & González-Aranda, J. M. (2021). ALL-Ready – Data Management Plan. ALL-Ready H2020 Project.

Ballon, P., Hoed, M., & Schuurman, D,. (2018) The effectiveness of involving users in digital innovation: Measuring the impact of living labs. *Telematics and Informatics*, 35 1201-1214.

Baregheh, A., Rowley, J., & Sambrook, S. (2009). Towards a multidisciplinary definition of innovation. *Management decision*, 47(8), 1323-1339.

Beaudoin, C., Joncoux, S., Jasmin, J. F., Berberi, A., McPhee, C., Schillo, R. S., & Nguyen, V. M. (2022). A research agenda for evaluating living labs as an open innovation model for environmental and agricultural sustainability. *Environmental Challenges*, 7, 100505.

Bellon-Maurel, V., Lutton, E., Bisquert, P., Brossard, L., Chambaron-Ginhac, S., Labarthe, P., Lagacherie, P., Martignac, F., Molenat, J., Parisey, N., Picault, S., Piot-Lepetit, I., & Vissier, I. (2022). Digital revolution for the agroecological transition of food systems: A responsible research and innovation perspective. *Agricultural Systems*, 203, p.103524.

Borgman, C. L. (2012). The conundrum of sharing research data. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63(6), 1059–1078.

Bronson, K., & Knezevic, I. (2016). Big Data in food and agriculture. *Big Data & Society*, 3(1), 2053951716648174.

Burgelman, J. C., Pascu, C., Szkuta, K., Von Schomberg, R., Karalopoulos, A., Repanas, K., & Schouppe, M. (2019). Open science, open data, and open scholarship: European policies to make science fit for the twenty-first century. *Frontiers in Big Data*, 2, 43.

Carolan, M. (2017). Agro-digital governance and life itself: food politics at the intersection of code and affect. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 57, 816-835.

Chesbrough, H. (2006). *Open innovation: The new imperative for creating and profiting from technology*. Harvard Business Press.

Chesbrough, H., & Di Minin, A. (2014). Open social innovation. In *New frontiers in open innovation* (pp. 169-188). Oxford University Press.

Clohessy, T., Morgan, L., & Acton, T. (2014). A theoretical framework for examining IT Governance in living laboratory ecosystems. In *Creating Value for All Through IT: IFIP WG 8.6 International Conference on Transfer and Diffusion of IT, TDIT 2014, Aalborg, Denmark, June 2-4, 2014*. Proceedings (pp. 334-344). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

Contreras, J. L. (2011). Bermuda's legacy: policy, patents and the design of the genome commons. *Minnesota Journal of Law, Science & Technology*, 12(1), 61-125.

Dedeurwaerdere, T. (2014). *Sustainability science for strong sustainability*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Del Giudice, M., G. Carayannis, E., Palacios-Marqués, D., Soto-Acosta, P., & Meissner, D. (2018). The human dimension of open innovation. *Management Decision*, 56(6), 1159-1166.

Efrat, K. (2014). The direct and indirect impact of culture on innovation. *Technovation*, 34(1), 12-20.

European Commission. (2012). *Access to and preservation of scientific information in Europe. Report on the implementation of Commission Recommendation C (2012) 4890 final—study*.

Francis, D., & Bessant, J. (2005). Targeting innovation and implications for capability development. *Technovation*, 25(3), 171-183.

García-Llorente, M., Pérez-Ramírez, I., Sabán de la Portilla, C., Haro, C., & Benito, A. (2019). Agroecological strategies for reactivating the agrarian sector: the case of Agrolab in Madrid. *Sustainability*, 11(4), 1181.

Greve, K., Vita, R. D., Leminen, S., & Westerlund, M. (2021). Living Labs: From niche to mainstream innovation management. *Sustainability*, 13(2), 791.

Hall, B. H., Helmers, C., Rogers, M., & Sena, V. (2014). The choice between formal and informal intellectual property: a review. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 52(2), 375-423.

Hess, C., & Ostrom, E. (2007). Understanding knowledge as a commons: From theory to practice. MIT Press.

Hidalgo, A., & Albors, J. (2008). Innovation management techniques and tools: a review from theory and practice. *R&D Management*, 38(2), 113-127.

ISO 56002. (2019). Innovation management — Innovation management system — Guidance.

Kamprath, M., & Mietzner, D. (2013). The impact of sectoral changes on individual competences: A reflective scenario study in the creative industries. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 80(2), 389-399.

Kratz, J. E., & Strasser, C. (2015). Researcher perspectives on publication and peer review of data. *PLoS One*, 10(2), e0117619.

Lam, A. (2005). Organisational innovation. In Fagerberg, J., Mowery, D. C., & Nelson, R. R. (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of innovation* (pp. 115-147). Oxford University Press.

Ladley, J. (2019). *Data governance: How to design, deploy, and sustain an effective data governance program*. Academic Press

Lazzarotti, V., Manzini, R., & Pellegrini, L. (2010). Open innovation models adopted in the bio-pharmaceutical industry: Evidence from European countries. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(10), 2076-2087.

Leonelli, S. (2016). *Data-centric biology: A philosophical study*. University of Chicago Press.

Long, C. (2010). Patent signals. *U. Chi. L. Rev.*, 69, 625.

López-Mosquera, N., García, T., & Barrena, R. (2014). An extension of the Theory of Planned Behavior to predict willingness to pay for the conservation of an urban park. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 135, 91-99.

Micheli, M., Ponti, M., Craglia, M., & Berti Suman, A. (2020). Emerging models of data governance in the age of datafication. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2), 2053951720948087.

McKiernan, E.C., Bourne, P.E., Brown, C.T., Buck, S., Kenall, A., Lin, J., McDougall, D., Nosek, B.A., Ram, K., Soderberg, C.K. and Spies, J.R., Thaney, K., Updegrove, A., Woo, K.H., & Yarkoni, T. (2016). How open science helps researchers succeed. *eLife*, 5, p.e16800.

McPhee, C., Bancercz, M., Mambrini-Doudet, M., Chrétien, F., Huyghe, C., & Gracia-Garza, J. (2021). The defining characteristics of agroecosystem living labs. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 1718.

Meijer, A. J. (2015). E-governance innovation: Barriers and strategies. *Government Information Quarterly*, 32(2), 198-206.

Micheli, M., Ponti, M., Craglia, M., & Berti Suman, A. (2020). Emerging models of data governance in the age of datafication. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2), 2053951720948087.

Murray, F., & Stern, S. (2007). Do formal intellectual property rights hinder the free flow of scientific knowledge?: An empirical test of the anti-commons hypothesis. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 63(4), 648-687.

Nielsen, M. (2011). *Reinventing discovery: The new era of networked science*. Princeton University Press.

Pila, J. (2017). *The Requirement for an Invention in Patent Law*. Oxford University Press.

Piwowar, H., Priem, J., Larivière, V., Alperin, J.P., Matthias, L., Norlander, B., Farley, A., West, J., & Haustein, S., (2018). The state of OA: a large-scale analysis of the prevalence and impact of Open Access articles. *PeerJ*, 6, e4375.

Roche, M., Prost, L., & Perret, S. (2020). Science, open science, and the role of data in the global south. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 86(1), e12123.

Ruijter, E. (2021). Designing and implementing data collaboratives: A governance perspective. *Government Information Quarterly*, 38(4), 101612.

Sridhar, V. (2019). *E Emerging ICT Policies and Regulations. Roadmap to Digital Economies*. Springer Nature.

Tenopir, C., Allard, S., Douglass, K., Aydinoglu, A. U., Wu, L., Read, E., Manoff, M., & Frame, M. (2011). Data sharing by scientists: practices and perceptions. *PLoS one*, 6(6), e21101.

Torremans, P. (2016). *Holyoak and Torremans Intellectual Property Law*. Oxford University Press.

Varga, C., Fehér, J., Fosselle, S., Vervoort, K., McKann, H., & Gascuel-Oudou, C. (2023). Reports of ALL-Ready pilot co-creation experiences v.1. ALL-Ready H2020 Project.

Wallis, J. C., Rolando, E., & Borgman, C. L. (2013). If we share data, will anyone use them? Data sharing and reuse in the long tail of science and technology. *PLoS one*, 8(7), e67332.

West, J., & Bogers, M. (2014). Leveraging external sources of innovation: a review of research on open innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 31(4), 814-831.

Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E. and Bouwman, J. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), 1-9.

Woelfle, M., Olliaro, P., & Todd, M. H. (2011). Open science is a research accelerator. *Nature Chemistry*, 3(10), 745-748.

Zawislak, P. A., Alves, A. C., Tello-Gamarra, J., Barbieux, D., & Reichert, F. M. (2012). Innovation capability: From technology development to transaction capability. *Journal of technology management & innovation*, 7(2), 14-27.

Zuiderwijk, A., & Janssen, M. (2014). Open data policies, their implementation and impact: A framework for comparison. *Government Information Quarterly*, 31(1), 17-29.

**ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure:
Preparation phase**

D6.5 Data principles and strategy for AgroEcoLLNet – 24 November 2023

6. Annex – Questionnaire results

Block 1: General data

N°	Type	Name of Living Lab (LL) or Research Infrastructure (RI)
1	LL	ÖMki On-Farm LL
1	LL	EMPHASIS
1	LL	LLAEBIO
1	RI	OasYs
1	LL	OCCITANUM
1	LL	INOFA SUPPORT OFFICE IKE
1	RI	LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre
1	LL	FiBL LL
1	LL	ROADMAP and ORGANIC RDD
1	RI	LifeWatch ERIC

Block 2: Innovation Management

2.1 How is the innovation process structured in your LL or RI?

Here, half of the respondents indicate that their innovation process is formal and documented, while the other half consider it an informal and undocumented process. Only one indicates not having a specific process. This result suggests a clear division in the way innovation is managed, and it could be related to factors such as the size of the organisation, its culture, its sector, among others.

2.1. How is the innovation process structured in your LL or RI?

	Value	Number
Formal, documented process		5
Informal, undocumented process		5
No specific process		1

11 respuestas

Figure 1 How is the innovation process structured in your LL or RI?

2.2 What methodologies does your LL or RI use to facilitate and manage innovation?

Most organisations seem to favor agile methods and Design Thinking. It is important to bear in mind that the use of these methodologies can affect the way innovation processes and barriers or challenges are managed.

2.2. What methodologies does your LL or RI use to facilitate and manage innovation?

	Value	Number
Design Thinking (Problem-solving approach that prioritises empathy, experimentation, and user-centric solutions)		6
Agile methods (Adaptable, iterative approach emphasising customer collaboration and responding to change)		8
Lean Startup (Startup methodology emphasising validated learning, customer feedback, and iterative design)		2
No specific methodology		3
To clarify: With being still being implemented, the innovatin management currently takes mainly place at the local facilities (which have developed and adapted different methods over their lifetime up to now). Thus, my box-ticking above illustrates the diversity of methods at the facilities (and not as structured approach by yet)		1

Figure 2 What methodologies does your LL or RI use to facilitate and manage innovation?

2.3 Can you provide examples of best practices in innovation management in your LL or RI?

Here, no quantifiable answers were provided, but it is important to observe the thematic trends in the responses. The bottom-up approach, formalisation of needs, and collaboration with national associations are mentioned.

2.3. Can you provide examples of good practices in innovation management in your LL or RI?

Value	Number
Yes	7
No	4

2.4 In case your previous answer is yes, can provide more information?

Varies

2.4. In case your previous answer is yes, can provide more information?

Bottom up approaches,

Formal expression of needs, call for innovative agtech project, formal contract between partners, reflexion on properties rights, evaluation process,

Representative of national meat association requesting proposal for improvement of grazing capacity of poor lands. Inofa proposing biostimulant-coated seeds of selected wild plants

Common agreement on how to establish the experimental phase.

I think it will need a bit more space and time

Co-designed prototyping and data processing automatism based on research needs

2.5 How is the success of innovations in your LL or RI measured and evaluated?

Most measure success based on the impact on key performance indicators, followed by the rate of use or adoption. These are valuable metrics that can indicate the effectiveness of the innovations implemented. However, the fact that some do not systematically measure or evaluate the success of innovations may represent an area for improvement.

Figure 3 How is the success of innovations in your LL or RI measured and evaluated?

2.6 Does your institution participate in collaborative innovation activities with external actors?

In general, there seems to be a high degree of collaboration, with most indicating that they always or often participate. Collaboration can be a key factor in driving innovation and overcoming identified barriers.

11 respuestas

Figure 4 Does your institution engage in collaborative innovation activities with external stakeholders?

2.7 What are the biggest barriers or challenges your LL or RI faces in terms of innovation management?

The lack of resources (time, funding) is the most commonly identified challenge, followed by resistance to change. These challenges are common in many organisations and must be addressed strategically to promote effective innovation.

2.7. What are the biggest barriers or challenges your LL or RI faces in terms of innovation management?

	Value	Number
Lack of resources (time, funding)	8	8
Resistance to change	5	5
Lack of clear innovation strategy	3	3
Lack of skills or knowledge	4	4
lack of time and lack of investment from researchers	1	1
Actually, not really a matter	1	1

Figure 5 What are the biggest barriers or challenges your LL or RI faces in terms of innovation management?

2.8 In your opinion, what are the main benefits or drivers of effective innovation management in your LL or RI?

ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure: Preparation phase

D6.5 Data principles and strategy for AgroEcoLLNet – 24 November 2023

The most frequent results are improved efficiency and productivity and more successful project outcomes. These drivers seem to be closely related to the ways in which organisations measure the success of innovations (question 2.5).

2.8. In your opinion, what are the main benefits or drivers of effective Innovation Management in your LL or RI?

	Value	Number
Improved efficiency and productivity		7
Increased creativity and idea generation		5
Enhanced competitiveness		1
More successful project outcomes		7
Greater customer/user satisfaction		6
Long-term user community building open to other innovation cycles.		1
Magnitude of changes		1
in the LL the driver was the challenge because the systemic change was not a requirement from the LL participants		1

Figure 6 In your opinion, what are the main benefits or drivers of effective Innovation Management in your LL or RI?

Block 3:

3.1 What policies or practices does your LL or RI have to facilitate open science and the use of open data?

Here, we see a slight majority that has formal and documented policies/practices, but a significant amount do not have specific policies/practices. This could indicate an opportunity to promote the adoption of formal policies and practices.

3.1. What policies or practices does your LL or RI have in place to facilitate open science and the use of open data?

	Value	Number
Formal, documented policies/practices		6
Informal, undocumented practices		2
No specific policies/practices		3

11 respuestas

Figure 7 What policies or practices does your LL or RI have in place to facilitate open science and the use of open data?

3.2 Are there specific initiatives to promote and encourage the use of open science and open data in your LL or RI?

The results are equally divided, suggesting that the promotion of open science and data may not be a priority for all organisations.

3.2. Are there specific initiatives to promote and foster the use of open science and open data in your LL or RI?

	Value	Number
Yes		5
No		6

11 respuestas

Figure 8 Are there specific initiatives to promote and foster the use of open science and open data in your LL or RI?

3.3 In case your company carries out specific initiatives to promote and encourage the use of open science and open data in your LL or RI, can you provide more information?

The answers to this question are not quantifiable, but there is a focus on training, the implementation of data management plans, and the use of metadata catalogs.

3.3. In case your company carries out specific initiatives to promote and foster the use of open science and open data in your LL or RI, can you provide more information?

<https://.../data-services>

Formation, data management plan ...

Publishing in open science; metadata available

It was done by the project

Implementation of the DMP; Metadata catalogue

3.4 What types of data does your LL or RI typically provide as open data, if any?

Processed or analysed data, metadata, and environmental data are the most commonly shared types of data. This could be related to the nature of the surveyed organisations.

3.4. What types of data does your LL or RI typically make available as open data, if any?

Value	Number
Raw data from experiments or observations	3
Processed or analysed data	5
Metadata (information about the data)	5
Data from literature reviews or bibliographic data	3
Social or economic data	1
Geographic or spatial data	3
Environmental data	5
Genetic or biological data	2
Not currently providing any open data	2

Digital technology data	1
Digital sensors in agricultural lands	1
We haven't discussed this yet. It depends on the data quality if our project is more indicative or if data show a statistically proven impact. We will for sure not publish farmers field journals open access due to data protection reasons.	1
Not relevant or only data on persons involved	1

Figure 9 What types of data does your LL or RI typically make available as open data, if any?

3.5 What methods do you use to ensure the quality of open data?

Most do not have specific methods to ensure the quality of open data, which could represent a risk for the effective use of these data.

3.5. Which of the following methods do you use to ensure the quality of open data?

Value	Number
Regular audits/reviews	1
Use of data standards	4
Training for data creators/providers	3
No specific methods	3
specific methods	1
Support for the implementation of harmonised data management systems at our facilities	1
no relevent	1

11 respuestas

Figure 10 Which of the following methods do you use to ensure the quality of open data?

3.6 How is training in open science and open data promoted in your LL or RI?

Here a lack of specific methods to promote training in open science and open data is observed. However, one-on-one mentoring and online resources or courses stand out as the most common strategies for those who do provide training.

3.6. How is training in open science and open data fostered in your LL or RI?

	Value	Number
Regular training sessions		0
Online courses or resources		2
One-to-one mentoring		3
No specific methods		6
Farmers are not interested in doing this. Researchers will be responsible and are trained for open access.		1
not relevant		1

11 respuestas

Figure 11 How is training in open science and open data fostered in your LL or RI?

3.7 What are the main challenges or barriers your LL or RI faces in terms of open science/open data?

Concerns about privacy and data security are the most cited challenge, followed by users' reluctance to share their data and insufficient technical skill or knowledge. These challenges could require specific training approaches and data management strategies to overcome.

Figure 12 What are the main challenges or barriers your LL or RI faces in terms of open science/open data?

3.8 How do you think the previous barrier can be overcome?

Collaboration with other institutions and additional training are the most common solutions suggested to overcome barriers in open science and data.

3.8. How do you think the previous barrier can be overcome?

Value	Number
Collaborate with other institutions to learn open data practices	5
Additional training	6

Increased funding or resources	2
Updating incentives within the scientific system; providing added value to individual careers when sharing FAIR data;	1
Recruit a person dedicated to data	1
Sharing of benefits with data owners	1
Acceptance that LL are dynamic and do not necessarily provide scientific sound data.	1
Not relevant	1
Awareness raising	1

Figure 13 How do you think the previous barrier can be overcome?

3.9 What do you consider to be the advantages or key drivers of promoting Open Science/Open Data in your LL or RI?

The most cited benefits are improved research transparency, wider dissemination of findings, and greater opportunities for collaboration. These drivers could be used to encourage the adoption of open science and data policies.

3.9. What do you perceive as the key advantages or drivers of promoting Open Science/Open Data in your LL or RI?

	Value	Number
Enhanced research transparency		9
Greater collaboration opportunities		7
Wider dissemination of research findings		8
Accelerated innovation		7
Increased public trust in research		6

Figure 14 What do you perceive as the key advantages or drivers of promoting Open Science/Open Data in your LL or RI?

Block 4

4.1 How does your LL or RI handle intellectual property rights (IPR) related to innovation and research?

In this question, most indicate that they do not have specific practices to handle IPR, which may indicate a lack of training or awareness about the importance of IPR.

Figure 15 How does your LL or RI handle IPR related to innovation and research?

4.2 What strategies does your institution use to protect its intellectual property?

Although the answers vary, there does not seem to be a dominant strategy for intellectual property protection. Trademarks and trade secrets are cited more frequently, but some indicate that they have none of the mentioned strategies.

We don't have any of the above	1
As mentioned above, IP issues are currently regulated at the level of local facilities (not yet on the pan-European level, where we are currently drafting IP policies to have them implemented once RI will be operational)	1
Do not know	3
Not yet functioning	1
Our LL produces knowledge accessible to all.	1
Licensing	1

11 respuestas

Figure 16 What strategies does your institution use to protect its intellectual property?

4.3 Can you provide more information about how your institution handle IPR related to innovation and research?

4.3. Can you provide more information about how your institution handle IPR related to innovation and research?

Value	Number
N/D	

4.4 How is intellectual property encouraged and secured in your LL or RI?

Mostly, there are no specific methods to encourage and secure intellectual property, which could indicate a lack of awareness or training in this area.

4.4. How is IPR fostered and ensured in your LL or RI?

Value	Number
Regular training on IPR	0
Clear communication of IPR policies	2
Monitoring and enforcement of IPR compliance	0
No specific methods	8
not relevant	1

ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure: Preparation phase

D6.5 Data principles and strategy for AgroEcoLLNet – 24 November 2023

11 respuestas

Figure 17 How is IPR fostered and ensured in your LL or RI?

4.5. Can you provide examples of good practices in IPR management in your LL or RI ?

4.5. Can you provide examples of good practices in IPR management in your LL or RI ?

	Value	Number
N/D		

4.6 What is the process when IPR infringements occur in your LL/RI?

Most indicate that they do not have a specific process to handle IPR infringements. This could be a barrier to effective intellectual property protection.

4.6. What is the process when IPR infringements occur in your LL/RI?

	Value	Number
Formal, documented process		1
Informal, undocumented process		0
No specific process		10

Figure 18 What is the process when IPR infringements occur in your LL/RI?

4.7 What are the main barriers or challenges your LL/RI faces in terms of IPR?

Understanding the complex IPR regulations and the time and cost associated with IPR are the most cited challenges. These challenges could be overcome with additional training and possibly collaboration with other institutions or IPR experts.

4.7. What are the main barriers or challenges your LL/RI faces in terms of IPR?

	Value	Number
Understanding complex IPR regulations		5
Time and cost associated with IPR		5
Protecting IP in international collaborations		2
Ensuring respect for IP rights		4
See situation on RI as described above.		1
Na		1
Not applicable		1
Not relevant		1

Figure 19 What are the main barriers or challenges your LL/RI faces in terms of IPR?

4.8 What are, in your opinion, the main benefits or motivators for robust intellectual property rights (IPR) management in your LL or RI?

The protection of innovative ideas and inventions, the prevention of misuse of proprietary information, and the enhancement of the organisation's reputation are the most cited benefits. These drivers could be used to encourage better IPR management.

4.8. In your view, what are the principal benefits or motivators for robust Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management in your LL or RI?

	Value	Number
Protection of innovative ideas and inventions		6
Facilitating commercial exploitation of research		4
Preventing misuse of proprietary information		5
Enhancing the organisation's reputation		4
Attracting investment or funding opportunities		3
Na		1
Not applicable		1
Not relevant. I think th a last part of the questions do not fit with roadmap II and also not with organic rdd. I might have misunderstood. If so please come back to me		1

Figure 20 In your view, what are the principal benefits or motivators for robust Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management in your LL or RI?